

Studies in Physico-Chemical Properties of Caseins. Part III. Viscosities of Casein Solutions in Different Alkalies

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The viscosities of one per cent solutions of caseins in sodium hydroxide and calcium hydroxide increase with rise in *pH* of the solution, due to progressive neutralisation of the various acid groups in caseins' upto *pH* 11 and then start decreasing. This gives a convenient method of estimating total base binding capacity of caseins. The maximum viscosity is higher in sodium hydroxide than in calcium hydroxide due, evidently, to greater ionisation of sodium caseinate than that of calcium caseinate. The viscosity in aqueous ammonia also increases with *pH* but it is not possible to go beyond *pH* 9.8 due to the weaker nature of the alkali. The viscosity at a given *pH* is higher in ammonia than in the other two alkalies. This is indicative of hydrogen bonding of ammonia with some of the groups in casein. Einstein equation has been used to ascertain the apparent degree of hydration of casein units in different alkalies. The axial ratios of casein molecules, as obtained from Kuhn equation based on the slope of the graph between specific viscosity and the volume fraction of the casein particles, are seen to be in good agreement with those obtained from the relationship with intrinsic viscosity suggested by Lauffer from experimental values based on diffusion, electron microscope and sedimentation techniques. The theoretical relationship suggested by Simha is similar, but the corresponding values are not quite close.

It is well known that alkaline solutions of proteins of moderate concentrations are truly viscous, as their rates of flow conform to Poiseuille's Law. It was thought of interest to study viscosities of caseins isolated from milk by different methods¹ in sodium hydroxide, calcium hydroxide and aqueous ammonia at different *pH* values. The results can be useful in indicating adhesiveness of these solutions besides giving an idea of degree of hydration and molecular shapes of casein particles.

EXPERIMENTAL

Casein samples were isolated from cows' milk as well as buffalos' milk by the Rennet, Hammersten, Zoller and Van Slyke-Bosworth methods described before¹. 0.025 g. portions of the various caseins (vacuum-dried over sulphuric acid) were taken in 50 ml. pyrex glass bottles and increasing amounts of standard solutions of sodium hydroxide, calcium hydroxide and aqueous ammonia (0.1 *N* in the case of sodium hydroxide and aqueous ammonia and 0.037 *N* in the case of calcium hydroxide) were added. The volumes were made upto 25 ml. so as to get 1% solution in every case. In some of the experiments, the amounts of casein were varied for the same final volume of 25 ml. with a view to get solutions of different concentrations varying from 0.2 to 4%. The viscosities of the solutions were measured

at 25°, 35° and 45° ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) using Ostwald viscometer. The densities were determined by the pycnometer method. The pH values were obtained by using glass electrode in conjunction with calomel electrode.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The relative viscosities of 1% solutions of different caseins in sodium hydroxide at 25° are plotted against the corresponding pH values in fig. 1. The curves have been extrapolated to relative viscosity equal to 1 at the respective pH values of isolation of the caseins, i.e. 6.6 in the case of Rennet casein and 4.6 in the case of the rest. It is seen that the viscosity increases upto a certain limit with increase in the pH value of the solution in every case, although the concentration remains the same all along. The values of the various caseins at a given pH value are seen to differ appreciably from one another. At pH 9.0, for example, the value for the Hammersten casein is the highest while that for the Van Slyke-Bosworth casein is the lowest. The Rennet casein could not be dissolved at this pH value to give 1% solution. The differences are maintained and even accentuated at pH 10.0 where Rennet casein also becomes sufficiently soluble.

Fig. 1. Viscosity—pH curves of one per cent casein solutions in sodium hydroxide at 25°.

In the pH range 10.8–11.0 where maximum viscosity is attained in very case, it is seen that the Rennet casein now gives the highest while the Van-Slyke Bosworth casein continues to give the lowest value. The Hammersten and Zoller caseins give values which are fairly close to each other and lie in between the two extremes, being, however, much nearer to the value for the Rennet casein than to that for the Van Slyke casein. The Rennet casein contained the largest amount of calcium of the order of 1%. Hammersten and Zoller caseins contained much smaller amounts, being only about 0.2%, while the Van Slyke casein was essentially free of all calcium. It appears that viscosity differences at high pH values are due to differences in calcium contents as has been shown by Beeby and Kumetal² in their experiments on concentrated skim milk.

The viscosities of the various caseins isolated from buffalos' milk show essentially the same features (Fig. 1b). The values, however, are slightly higher than those of the corresponding samples isolated from cows' milk. This may, again, be due to minor differences in the compositions, particularly in regard to calcium contents, of cows' and buffalos' milk.

It may be noted, incidentally, that Rennet caseins, on account of their appreciably higher viscosities at high pH values, appear to be better suited for adhesive purposes.

The increase in viscosity with gradual increase in the pH of the medium appears to be due to successive neutralisations of the various acidic groups which are known to ionise at increasing pH values¹. This leads to the formation of increasing amounts of the largely hydrated caseinate ions which, at appreciable concentrations, start aggregating giving rise to hydrated casein micelles. Due to the Donnan membrane effect, the concentration of the ions within the micelles increases more rapidly than that in the solution resulting in greater and greater increase in viscosity, as actually observed. According to this view the point of maximum viscosity should occur at the point of complete neutralisation of the casein. This is actually the case since the point of maximum viscosity (Fig. 1) and that of complete neutralisation¹, both occur in the pH range 10.8–11.0. It was found, further, that the amount of alkali required to be added to bring a casein solution at its maximum viscosity was very close to the amount needed for complete neutralisation, as read from the pH -titration curve of the casein. The two sets of values are recorded in Table 1. This observation, incidentally, places at our disposal a far simpler method of estimating total base-binding capacity of caseins. All that has to be done is to determine viscosity of casein solution of a given concentration on adding increasing amounts of sodium hydroxide, to plot a graph between the viscosity and the amount of alkali added and to interpolate, from the graph, the amount of alkali corresponding to the maximum in the graph.

The decline in viscosity on continued addition of sodium hydroxide after complete neutralisation of the acidic groups may be partly due to the break down or denaturation of the casein structure and partly due to the suppression of ionisation of sodium caseinate and the presence of the unreacted alkali which itself has a much lower viscosity.

The values obtained with a 4% solution of one of the caseins (Hammersten casein, isolated from cows' milk), included in Fig. 1a, also indicate the same trends. The maximum occurs at about the same pH value as in the case of 1% solution. The amount of alkali

TABLE 1

Base binding capacities of various caseins as obtained from (i) viscosity measurements on the addition of increasing amounts of sodium hydroxide and (ii) pH-titration curves

Description of casein	Base binding capacities (eq/10 ⁵ g. casein) from	
	Viscosity measurements	pH-titration curves
<i>Cows' caseins</i>		
Rennet	70	66
Hammarsten	98	96
Zoller	112	108
Vanslyke-Bosworth	98	100
<i>Buffalos' caseins</i>		
Rennet	56	52
Hammarsten	93	90
Zoller	108	100
Vanslyke-Bosworth	91	90

required per g. casein for the maximum value of viscosity was also found to be the same as before.

The results of casein solutions in calcium hydroxide are shown in Fig. 2. The Rennet casein, isolated from cows' milk, could not be used on account of its low solubility in this medium. The rise in viscosity with pH is seen now to be much less steep, particularly upto pH 9.5. The maximum value is also seen to be much less than that observed on the addition of sodium hydroxide. This appears to be due to the fact that calcium caseinate is much less ionised than sodium caseinate.

The results for solutions in aqueous ammonia are plotted in Fig. 3. The neutralisation in this case could not be pushed beyond pH 9.8, as ammonia is a weak base. The maximum in the pH-viscosity curve, therefore, could not be realised.

The viscosity values of the various caseins in sodium hydroxide, calcium hydroxide and aqueous ammonia at corresponding pH values as interpolated from the appropriate graphs, are given in Table 2. It is seen that the values at a given pH decrease in the order $\text{NH}_3 > \text{NaOH} > \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$. The higher values in ammonia appear to be due to hydrogen bonding of the molecule with some of the functional groups, particularly the phenolic and ϵ amino groups which remain unneutralised even at appreciably high pH values. In this connection, it may also be noted that casein is known to swell much more in aqueous ammonia than in other alkalies³.

Einstein equation⁴, although applicable, strictly speaking, to solutions or suspensions of spherical particles, has often been used for ascertaining the degree of hydration of the

Fig. 2. Viscosity—pH curves of one per cent casein solutions in calcium hydroxide at 25°.

Fig. 3. Viscosity—pH curves of one per cent casein solutions in aqueous ammonia.

TABLE 2

Viscosities of alkaline solutions of various caseins in sodium hydroxide, calcium hydroxide and aqueous ammonia at corresponding pH values

Description of the sample	pH	Viscosities in different alkalies		
		Sodium hydroxide	Calcium hydroxide	Aqueous ammonia
<i>Cows' caseins</i>				
Hammarsten	7.0	1.055	1.041	1.122
	8.0	1.090	1.080	1.160
	9.0	1.158	1.090	1.208
	9.5	1.203	1.097	1.238
Zoller	7.0	1.045	1.057	1.100
	8.0	1.078	1.070	1.145
	9.0	1.134	1.082	1.194
	9.5	1.180	1.088	1.220
Vanslyke Bosworth	7.0	1.030	1.037	1.063
	8.0	1.062	1.050	1.110
	9.0	1.113	1.062	1.175
	9.5	1.150	1.070	1.208
<i>Buffalos' caseins</i>				
Hammarsten	7.0	1.157	1.127	1.170
	8.0	1.177	1.139	1.203
	9.0	1.207	1.158	1.247
	9.5	1.230	1.165	1.288
Zoller	7.0	1.140	1.123	1.154
	8.0	1.158	1.135	1.178
	9.0	1.178	1.150	1.215
	9.5	1.188	1.158	1.236
Vanslyke Bosworth	7.0	1.127	1.067	1.137
	8.0	1.145	1.077	1.156
	9.0	1.163	1.090	1.188
	9.5	1.172	1.097	1.205

constituent units in macromolecular as well as lyophilic colloidal solution. According to this equation

$$\text{specific viscosity} = \eta_{sp} = \frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0} = 2.5 G$$

where η_0 is the viscosity of the pure solvent at a given temperature, η is that of the solution at the same temperature and G is the fraction of the total volume occupied by the solute particles in the whole of the solution.

The ratio of the specific hydrodynamic volume of a lyophilic colloid obtained from the above equation to the true specific volume in the dry state has been taken by a number of workers as a measure of the degree of hydration (or solvation) of the particles⁵⁻⁶. The values of this ratio in the case of solutions of different caseins in sodium hydroxide as well as calcium hydroxide at the points corresponding to maximum viscosity values at 25° and 45° are recorded in Table 3. It is seen that the degree of hydration, which, evidently, is

much more in sodium hydroxide than in calcium hydroxide, decreases appreciably with rise in temperature in all cases. The Rennet casein is seen to be much more hydrophilic than any other variety of casein included in the present investigations.

TABLE 3

The ratio of specific hydrodynamic volume to the true specific volume in alkaline solutions of different caseins at 25° and 45°

Description of casein	In sodium hydroxide solution				In calcium hydroxide solution			
	Cows' caseins		Buffalos' caseins		Cows' casein		Buffalos' casein	
	25°	45°	25°	45°	25°	45°	25°	45°
Rennet	21.495	8.321	23.126	13.342	—	—	18.467	10.635
Hammarston	19.180	10.960	22.581	12.069	11.234	6.367	13.152	7.039
Zoller	18.356	12.555	19.728	16.188	9.590	6.556	11.998	9.681
Vanslyke Bosworth	15.070	6.208	15.892	11.182	6.402	2.573	7.302	5.135

The validity of the Einstein equation, however, is limited since the protein molecules are not spherical. The values recorded in Table 3, therefore, may be taken as approximate giving, at best, only comparative figures for the degrees of hydration of casein units in different cases.

The viscosity data has been used by some workers^{7,8} to get an idea of the shape, or, to be more exact, the axial ratios of protein molecules by using Kuhn equation⁹.

$$K = 2.5 + (a/b)^2.1/16$$

where K is the slope of the graph plotted between specific viscosity and volume fraction of the solute particles, and a and b are the major and minor axes of the molecule. In order to apply this equation, we determined specific viscosities of casein solutions of concentrations varying from 0.2 to 2 per cent by weight (or from 0.146 to 1.46% by volume, taking density of dry casein as 1.37) in sodium hydroxide. The plots, as shown for some of the samples, in Fig. 4 were quite linear. The values of the slopes, therefore, could easily be obtained.

The axial ratios, as obtained from the Kuhn equation, are recorded in Table 4. The high values indicate that the particles are rod-shaped rather than cubic or spherical. The axial ratio falls, however, on raising the temperature from 25° to 45°. Since no appreciable break down of the casein structure is expected to take place within this temperature range it appears that the particles have a tendency to change to cubic or spherical structures with rise in temperature.

Lauffer¹⁰ attempted to work out a correlation between volume fraction intrinsic viscosity, $G \rightarrow_0 [\eta_{sp}/G]$ and axial ratio, as determined for different proteins by using diffusion, electron microscopic and sedimentation methods by various workers. His plot is reproduced in Fig. 5. The intrinsic viscosities of our results at the various temperatures are given in Table 5. The plot of these values against the corresponding axial ratios is included in Fig. 5. There is a fairly good agreement between the two.

Fig. 4. Relationship between specific viscosity and volume fraction of casein in sodium hydroxide at pH 9.6.

Fig. 5. Relationship between volume intrinsic viscosity and axial ratio (a/b).

TABLE 4

Axial ratios of casein molecules at different temperatures in sodium hydroxide solutions at pH 9.6 as calculated from Kuhn equation

Description of the sample	Cows' caseins			Buffalos' caseins		
	25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°
Hammarsten	20.2	18.1	15.7	20.7	18.8	15.5
Zoller	23.8	22.1	19.6	24.2	23.1	21.7
Vanslyke Bosworth	22.8	18.9	13.6	19.8	18.1	16.0

TABLE 5

Volume intrinsic viscosities of casein solutions at pH 9.6 at different temperatures

Description of casein	Cows' caseins			Buffalos' caseins		
	25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°
Rennet	21	16	8	23	19	15
Hammarsten	24	20	16	30	21	15
Zoller	38	33	24	37	35	30
Vanslyke-Bosworth	34	22	16	27	22	18

Sinha¹¹ worked out, theoretically, a relationship between intrinsic viscosity and axial ratio of rod shaped particles. His graph also included in Fig. 5, is seen to be similar to the two experimental curves. However, it gives slightly different axial ratios for the same intrinsic viscosities, the differences increase with increase in intrinsic viscosity. It appears that Brownian motion which has been considered rigorously by Sinha in his treatment is not operative to that extent in the case of relatively larger caseinate micellar aggregates in alkaline solutions included in the present investigations.

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